

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Mercury(II)

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Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide has been used to determine 12 to 32 mg of mercury(II) gravimetrically. The complex is precipitated quantitatively within the pH range, 2.5 to 9.0. Mercury(II) has been separated from Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} or WO_4^{2-} using citrate, tartrate or fluoride as masking agent. However, Ag^+ , Tl^+ or Cd^{2+} does not precipitate under the conditions Hg^{2+} does. The precipitate is weighed after drying as $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$ containing 26.19% of mercury as it is stable up to 220°. The standard deviation is $\pm 0.13\%$.

ORGANIC reagents forming thermally stable complexes with mercury(II) as well as having selectivity towards this ion are few in number. Among these, the precipitants containing nitrogen or sulphur¹⁻⁷ out-number oxygenated reagents⁸⁻¹¹ since this metal ion exhibits greater affinity for polarisable ligand atoms¹². In this investigation it has been shown that, benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide, a ligand generally suitable for metals with affinity for oxygen atoms^{13,14} is also useful as a gravimetric reagent for mercury(II). The mercury(II)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex is thermally stable and the procedure described for the determination is selective provided the experimental conditions are chosen carefully.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide: The reagent was prepared in the laboratory¹³. An ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

Mercury(II) solution: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving mercury(II) nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) in 0.1 *M* nitric acid. The metal content was determined gravimetrically^{11,15}.

Diverse ions: Aqueous solutions of other metal ions were prepared from sulphates, chlorides or nitrates. For studying the effects of different anions including tungstate either sodium or potassium salt was used.

All the reagents were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

Apparatus: A battery operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used for measuring the pH-values. A pen-recording Aminco thermoanalyser was used for the thermal decomposition study of the complex.

Procedure: An aliquot of the stock solution containing 12.0 to 32.0 mg of mercury(II) was diluted to 150 ml and the pH was adjusted at 3.5-4.0 with

sodium acetate solution. The mixture was heated to boiling and 15 ml of an ethanolic solution of the reagent (70 to 140 mg) was added with stirring. The precipitate formed was digested on a hot water-bath for 20 to 25 min with occasional stirring. The complex was filtered on a sintered glass crucible, washed with hot (80°) water and dried to constant weight at 120°. The metal content of the complex was obtained using a factor 0.2619. The results of these determinations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF MERCURY(II)

Hg taken, (mg)	Wt. of complex, (mg)	Hg found, (mg)	Rel. Error, (%)
31.80	121.8	31.90	+0.31
	121.2	31.74	-0.19
25.44	97.2	25.46	+0.08
	97.5	25.54	+0.39
19.08	72.8	19.06	-0.10
	73.3	19.20	+0.63
12.72	48.6	12.73	+0.08
	48.9	12.80	+0.63

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: Separation of mercury(II) from reasonable amounts of cadmium(II), thallium(I) or silver(I) was possible following the procedure described above.

However, 1.0 g of citric acid was added and the pH was adjusted to 4.0 before the addition of the reagent to effect separation of mercury(II) from copper(II) and zinc(II), while sodium potassium tartrate (1.0 g) was used to mask manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), lead(II), bismuth(III), aluminium(III), uranium(VI) and tungsten(VI). For masking iron(III), ammonium fluoride (1.0 g) was used. The pH was maintained between 5.0 and 5.5 while effecting these separations and the initial washing was carried out with hot water containing a little of

the masking agent. Hot water was used for the final washing. Chloride and reasonable amounts of bromide did not interfere with the determination though iodide completely masked the reaction.

The results of separation of mercury(II) from various other metal ions are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2. SEPARATION OF MERCURY(II)* FOR DIVERSE IONS

Diverse (mg)	Ion	Masking agent	Wt. of complex (mg)	Hg found, (mg)	Rel. Error (%)
Ag ⁺	50	—	121.6	31.84	+0.13
			121.2	31.74	-0.19
Tl ⁺	50	—	122.2	32.01	+0.66
			122.0	31.96	+0.50
Cd ²⁺	50	—	121.2	31.74	-0.19
			121.2	31.74	-0.19
Cu ²⁺	50	(a)	121.6	31.84	+0.13
			121.2	31.74	-0.19
Co ²⁺	50	(b)	122.2	32.01	+0.66
			122.2	32.01	+0.66
Pb ²⁺	50	(b)	121.6	31.84	+0.13
			121.6	31.84	+0.13
Ni ²⁺	50	(b)	121.6	31.84	+0.13
			121.6	31.84	+0.13
Mn ²⁺	50	(b)	121.0	31.69	-0.35
			121.5	31.82	+0.06
Zn ²⁺	50	(a)	121.9	31.91	+0.35
			121.6	31.84	+0.13
Bi ³⁺	50	(b)	122.2	32.01	+0.66
			122.0	31.96	+0.50
Al ³⁺	50	(b)	122.2	32.01	+0.66
			122.2	32.01	+0.66
Fe ³⁺	50	(c)	122.0	31.96	+0.50
			121.7	31.86	+0.19
Cr ³⁺	50	(b)	121.5	31.82	+0.06
			121.6	31.84	+0.13
UO ₂ ²⁺	50	(b)	121.7	31.86	+0.19
			121.5	31.82	+0.06
WO ₄ ²⁻	50	(b)	122.2	32.01	+0.66
			122.2	32.01	+0.66

*Hg taken 31.80mg.

(a) citrate, (b) tartrate, (c) fluoride.

Results and Discussion

Properties and Composition of the complex : The light yellow mercury(II)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex decomposed very slowly when exposed to sunlight developing a grey to black tinge. The freshly precipitated complex was soluble in chloroform or isobutyl methyl ketone.

The nitrogen content of the complex was determined by Kjeldahl's method using glucose for the reduction of nitro-group. The experimental results—N7.32, 7.34% (theo. 7.31%) were in agreement with the formula assigned, Hg(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂ containing 26.19% of mercury.

Thermal decomposition studies : Thermogravimetric analysis of mercury(II)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide showed that the complex was stable up to 220°; then it started decomposing probably through HgO (weight loss, observed 72.0%, required 71.8%) to mercury, which finally volatilised. The thermogram is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Thermogram of Mercury(II)-Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide.

Effect of pH : A set of experiments was carried out under similar conditions using fixed quantities of mercury(II) (30.4 mg) and the reagent (130 mg) but varying the pH. The range of quantitative precipitation was found to be 2.5 to 9.0.

Effect of the concentration of the reagent : In another series of experiments the pH was fixed at 4.0 and the amount of the reagent was varied. It was observed that for the quantitative determination of mercury(II), the supernatant solution after the precipitation should be above 0.005% and below 0.02% with respect to the reagent. Higher reagent concentrations resulted in some contamination of the reagent in the precipitate.

Effect of sequestering agents : The presence of tartaric, citric or nitrilotriacetic acid as well as that of fluoride did not interfere with the determination of mercury(II). The precipitation was slow and homogeneous in the presence of nitrilotriacetic acid. In these studies the pH was maintained at 5.0 to 5.5.

However, the precipitation was partially inhibited by sulphosalicylic acid and completely so by disodium-EDTA, magnesium-EDTA, thioglycolic acid, ascorbic acid and iodide.

Precision and Accuracy : The standard deviation for 30 determinations of mercury(II) (12 to 32 mg in 150 ml) by the method described was found to be $\pm 0.13\%$.

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